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**ESTIMATION OF SURFACE RUNOFF BY SCS CURVE NUMBER
MODEL FOR HAROHALLI WATERSHED**

Nanjundi.P¹, Dr.M.Inayathulla², Sandhya M. C³, Ravindranath C⁴

Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, NMIT, Bangalore-560064.Karnataka, India.

Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, UVCE, Bangalore-560056.Karnataka, India.

ME student in Department of Civil Engineering, UVCE, Bangalore -560056.Karnataka, India

Research student in Department of Civil Engineering, SIT, Tumkur .Karnataka, India.

Abstract

Runoff is one of the most important hydrological variables used in most of the water resources applications. In the present study Harohalli watershed, Kanakapura Taluk, Ramanagara District area was chosen since it falls in the rocks and granite area of Karnataka state, India is carried out using SCS and GIS techniques. The study area covers an area of 281.56 km² and comprises of eleven micro watersheds. Physiographically the area is characterized by undulating topography with plains and shallow valleys. The Soil Conservation Service Curve Number (SCS CN) also known as hydrologic soil group method was used in this study. This method is a versatile and popular approach for quick runoff estimation and is relatively easy to use with minimum data and it gives adequate result. From the study, monthly as well as annual rainfall and corresponding runoff were estimated.

KEYWORDS: Estimation, Infiltration, Landuse, Rainfall, Runoff, Watershed

Introduction

Runoff means the drainage of flowing off of precipitation from a watershed area through a surface channel. It thus represents the output from the watershed in a given unit of time. For efficient design, planning and management of river watershed projects estimation of runoff magnitude is necessary to

determine the quantity of surface runoff that takes place in any river watershed, understanding the complex rainfall and runoff processes, which depends on many geomorphological and climate factors are necessary. In the present study, the information such as land use / land cover and hydrological soil group derived from remotely sensed data were integrated through Arc GIS software to assign the curve number on polygon wise to estimate surface runoff using SCS curve number model.

Depending on the type of problem, availability of data and prevailing runoff mechanism the hydraulic engineers recommend curve number procedure of

the United States Department of agriculture Soil Conservation Services (USDA, SCS, 1972) to compute surface runoff in small to medium sized ungauged basins, probably due to its apparent simplicity. Hence in the present study USDA SCS curve number method was adopted to estimate runoff.

1.2 Soil Conservation Service (SCS) Curve Number Model

Accurate estimation of surface runoff is difficult as it depends on many factors. Soil Conservation Service (SCS) Curve Number model is one of the method to estimate surface runoff. This method described by Soil Conservation Services (1985) was evolved for uniform rainfall using the assumptions for a triangular hydrograph. In this method, runoff will be determined as a function of current soil moisture content, static soil conditions, and management practices. Runoff is deducted from the water available to enter the soil prior to infiltration.

The SCS approach has been considered as a popular method for runoff modeling because of the following reasons:

- Its use has been mandated by the United States Department of Agriculture;
- It provides reasonable and useful results for average conditions;
- There is a large user base available to assist new users and much is known about how to vary the parameters for non-standard conditions;
- It is very easy to understand and requires few resources to use.

Fig. 1.1 Methodology to estimate surface runoff by SCS Curve number model

The SCS developed an index, which is called as the runoff Curve Number (CN) to represent the combined hydrologic effect of soil, land use, agriculture treatment class, hydrologic condition and antecedent soil moisture. These factors can be accessed from soil surveys, site investigations and land use map, while using the SCS hydrologic models for design.

The specification of antecedent moisture condition is often a policy decision that suggests the average watershed conditions rather than recognition of a hydrologic condition at a particular time and place. Fig 1.1 shows the methodology followed to estimate surface runoff by SCS Curve Number model.

The SCS curve number method is based on the water balance equation and two fundamental hypotheses.

- Ratio of the actual direct runoff to the potential runoff is equal to the ratio of the actual infiltration to the potential infiltration.
- The amount of initial abstraction is some fraction of the potential infiltration.

Expressed mathematically as,

$$\frac{Q}{P-I_a} = \frac{F}{S} \tag{1.1}$$

Where Q is the runoff, P is the rainfall and F is the actual infiltration and it is the difference between the potential and accumulated runoff. I_a is initial abstraction, which represents all the losses before the runoff begins. It includes water retained in surface depressions, water intercepted by vegetation, and initial infiltration. This is highly variable but generally is correlated with soil and land cover parameters; S is the potential infiltration after the runoff begins ($S > F$).

Thus, a runoff curve number is defined to relate the unknown S as a spatially distributed variables as,

$$CN = \frac{25400}{S+254} \tag{1.2}$$

Or

$$S = \frac{25400}{CN} - 254 \tag{1.3}$$

$$Q = \frac{(P-0.2S)^2}{(P+0.8S)} \tag{1.4}$$

1.2.1 Determination of Curve Number (CN)

The curve number is an index that represents the combination of hydrologic soil group and antecedent moisture conditions. The curve number value is determined from hydrological soil group and antecedent moisture conditions of the watershed. For curve number determination the land use/land cover and hydrological soil group map were integrated and based on their combinations the curve number were selected from the available source. Table 1.1 shows the curve number (AMC II) available in the literature to estimate runoff.

The CN value were obtained after integrating the land use / land cover map and hydrological soil group map which were prepared from the remotely sensed data.

Table 1.1 Runoff Curve Numbers for (AMC II) hydrologic soil cover complex

Sl No	Land use	Hydrologic Soil Group			
		A	B	C	D
1	Agricultural land without conservation (Kharif)	72	81	88	91
2	Double crop	62	71	88	91
3	Agriculture Plantation	45	53	67	72
4	Land with scrub	36	60	73	79
5	Land without scrub (Stony waste/rock outcrops)	45	66	77	83
6	Forest (degraded)	45	66	77	83
7	Forest Plantation	25	55	70	77
8	Grass land/pasture	39	61	74	80
9	Settlement	57	72	81	86
10	Road/railway line	98	98	98	98
11	River/Stream	97	97	97	97
12	Tanks without water	96	96	96	96
13	Tank with water	100	100	100	100

(Source: Ven Te Chow, 1981)

1.2.2 Hydrological Soil Group Classification

The hydrologic soil groups as defined by the Soil Conservation Service (1972) were classified into A, B, C and D according to their minimum infiltration rate. The hydrologic soil group was used to get curve number from look up Table 5.1. The hydrologic soil groups, as defined by SCS soil scientist are as follows.

Group A

Soils in this group have a low runoff potential (high-infiltration rates) even when thoroughly wetted. They consist of deep, well to excessively well-drained sands or gravels. These soils have a high rate of water transmission.

Group B

Soils in this group have moderate infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted and consists chiefly of moderately deep to deep, well-drained to moderately well-drained soils with moderately fine to moderately coarse textures. These soils have a moderate rate of water transmission.

Group C

Soils have slow infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted and consist chiefly of

soils with a layer that impedes the downward movement of water, or soils with moderately fine-to fine texture. These soils have a slow rate of water transmission.

Group D

Soils have a high runoff potential (very slow infiltration rates) when thoroughly wetted. These soils consist chiefly of clay soils with high swelling potential, soils with a permanent high-water table, soils with a clay layer near the surface, and shallow soils over nearly impervious material. These soils have a very slow rate of water transmission.

The identification of the particular SCS soil group at a site can be done by one of the following three ways: (i) soil characteristics (ii) county soil surveys and (iii) minimum infiltration rates. Soil analysis can be used to estimate the minimum infiltration rates, to classify the soils using the values shown in Table 1.2. Based on the soil infiltration rate, the soil series of the watershed was assigned as A, B, C and D.

Fig.1.3 shows the Hydrological Soil Group map prepared by assigning hydrological soil group based on the infiltration rate.

Fig. 1.2 Land use/ land cover Map of Harohalli watershed

Table 1.2 Minimum infiltration rates associated with each soil group (Mc Cuen, 1982)

Group	Minimum infiltration rate (cm/hr)
A	0.76
B	0.38-0.76
C	0.13-0.38
D	0.0-0.13

Table 1.3 Spatial distribution of Land use/ land cover classification for Harohalli watershed

Sl.no	Land use/Land cover	Area(Sq.km)	% of Area
1	Agricultural Plantation	34.06	12.10
2	Barren Rocky / Stony Waste / Sheet Rock Area	6.79	2.41
3	Crop land	142.23	50.52
4	Degraded Forest	1.13	0.40
5	Fallow land	5.30	1.88
6	Forest Plantations	0.046	0.016
7	Gullied / Revinous Land	0.30	0.11
8	Industrial Area	1.67	0.59
9	Lake / Tanks	7.84	2.78

10	Land with scrub	24.16	8.58
11	Land without scrub	0.32	0.12
12	Mining / Industrial Wasteland	5.67	2.02
13	Mixed Vegetation	0.29	0.11
14	Moist & Dry Deciduous Forest	27.79	9.87
15	River / Stream	0.97	0.34
16	Scrub Forest	4.18	1.48
17	Town / Cities	14.16	5.03
18	Village	4.64	1.65
	Total	281.56	100

Table 1.4 Hydrological Soil Group assigned for soils in the watershed

Sl.No	Hydrological Soil Group (HSG)	Area (Sq. km)	% of Area
1	B	178.83	63.51
2	C	53.56	19.02
3	D	49.18	17.47
	TOTAL	281.56	100.00

Fig. 1.3 Hydrological Soil Group Map of Harohalli watershed

1.2.3 Antecedent Moisture Condition (AMCs)

Antecedent Moisture Condition (AMC) refers to the water content present in the soil at a given time. The AMC value is intended to reflect the effect of infiltration on both the volume and rate of runoff according to the infiltration curve. The SCS developed three antecedent soil-moisture conditions and labeled them as I, II, III. These AMC's correspond to the following

soil conditions. Table 1.5 shows the AMC's classification.

AMC I: Soils are dry but not to the wilting point; satisfactory cultivation has taken place.

AMC II: Average conditions.

AMC III: Heavy rainfall or light rainfall and low temperatures have occurred within last 5 days; Saturated soils. Table shows the seasonal rainfall units for the AMC classification and for CN.

Table 1.5 Antecedent Moisture Condition (AMCs)

AMCs	FIVE DAYS ANTECEDENT RAINFALL (mm)	
	Dormant season	Growing season
I	< 12.7 mm	<35.56 mm
II	12.7-27.94 mm	35.56-53.34 mm
III	> 27.94 mm	53.34 mm

The Value of CN is shown for AMC II and for a variety of land uses, soil treatment, or farming practices. The hydrologic condition refers to the state of the vegetation growth. The Curve Number values for AMC-I and AMC-III can be obtained from AMC-II by the method of conservation. The empirical CN_1 and CN_3 equations for conservation methods are as follows:

$$CN_1 = \frac{CN_2}{2.281 - 0.01281CN_2} \quad (1.5)$$

$$CN_3 = \frac{CN_2}{0.427 + 0.00573CN_2} \quad (1.6)$$

Table 1.6 shows the weighted curve numbers estimated for watersheds within the watershed. All the three

AMC conditions were considered for the estimation of runoff from the watershed. Fig. 5.5 shows the curve number map prepared by integrating land use / land cover and hydrological soil group map through Arc GIS software. The quantity of runoff estimated from each watershed is tabulated in Table 5.8.

A weighted runoff was estimated for the watershed as

$$WeightedQ = \frac{(A_1 * q_1 + A_2 * q_2 + \dots + A_n * q_n)}{(A_1 + A_2 + \dots + A_n)} \quad (1.7)$$

Where $A_1, A_2 \dots A_n$ are the areas of the watersheds having respective runoff $q_1, q_2 \dots q_n$. The weighted runoff approach was again extended to quantify the total amount of runoff from the entire watershed.

Fig 1.4 Flowchart showing the procedure to derive the Weighted Curve Numbers

Table 1.6 Sub-Watershed wise weighted curve numbers

Watershed No	Area (Sq. Km)	CN I	CN II	CN III
1	15.61	64.60	80.63	90.69
2	15.97	54.34	73.07	86.41
3	37.07	56.53	74.79	87.42
4	37.27	50.98	70.34	84.74
5	21.47	61.70	78.61	89.59
6	27.16	54.44	73.16	86.46
7	30.02	59.11	76.73	88.54
8	13.38	62.95	79.49	90.08
9	19.36	62.83	79.41	90.03
10	20.98	60.22	77.54	88.99
11	43.25	57.07	75.20	87.65

Fig. 1.5 curve number map of Harohalli watershed

Table 1.7(a): Watershed wise runoff (mm) estimated using SCS curve number model

Years	Watershed No.									
	1		2		3		4		5	
	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO
1998	930.9	330.91	930.9	241.03	930.9	259.44	1387.3	418.08	770	175
1999	1157.6	368.06	1157.6	261.89	1157.6	283.82	1518.4	400.6	1090.3	381.32
2000	1230.4	520.71	1230.4	409.55	1230.4	433.02	1374	337.22	1127.7	386.82
2001	972	324.82	972	243.82	972	242.66	886.6	251.25	614.2	170.28
2002	470.5	13.91	470.5	6.59	470.5	7.7	669.3	201.47	544.3	90.27
2003	1016.9	180.17	1016.9	106.97	1016.9	120.77	617.8	35.87	400.5	32.65

2004	1040.6	240.43	1040.6	175.55	1040.6	188.36	1111.2	194.4	972.7	306.11
2005	1197.4	406.22	1197.4	289.27	1197.4	312.98	1204.2	286.05	1318.5	330.63
2006	500.8	68.41	500.8	42.05	500.8	46.89	417.2	30.59	402.6	102.76
2007	744.6	132.24	744.6	87.25	744.6	95.78	1076.6	198.94	586.0	56.65
2008	940.8	275.43	940.8	199.72	940.8	215.16	1079.8	265.66	823.7	125.72
2009	921.3	275.14	921.3	200.41	921.3	215.52	1196.5	323.86	951.3	340.54
2010	535.8	111.32	535.8	73.85	535.8	75.49	898.8	156.68	682.6	123.02
2011	633.1	212.07	633.1	153.96	633.1	165.69	903.2	195.81	672.5	181.69
2012	323	99.87	323	70.31	323	76.28	584.4	114.36	421.2	160.62
Average	841.05	237.31	841.05	170.8	841.05	182.64	995.02	227.4	758.54	197.6

RF: Rainfall , RO: Runoff

Table 1.7(b): Watershed wise runoff (mm) estimated using SCS curve number model

Year	Watershed No.											
	6		7		8		9		10		11	
	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO	RF	RO
1998	1021.6	294.23	1021.6	335.08	770	181.89	1021.6	368.64	770	167.04	770	151.00
1999	1130.5	242.46	1130.5	285.95	1090.3	794.45	1130.5	322.36	1090.3	362.77	1090.3	324.71
2000	1245.9	230.97	1245.9	319.29	1127.7	400.97	1245.9	358.32	1127.7	342.08	1127.7	336.04
2001	899.8	192.56	899.8	227.06	614.2	174.61	899.8	255.90	614.2	154.92	614.2	154.78
2002	496.1	35.16	496.1	44.29	544.3	94.3	496.1	52.48	544.3	77.48	544.3	76.25
2003	556.2	54.78	556.2	66.46	400.5	34.55	556.2	76.80	400.5	28.42	400.5	26.45
2004	1080.7	280.24	1080.7	317.54	972.7	316.52	1080.7	348.31	972.7	270.00	972.7	268.39

2005	1273.8	300.71	1273.8	349.04	1318.5	343.47	1273.8	390.11	1318.5	286.95	1318.5	285.23
2006	402.6	82.11	402.6	95.31	402.6	106.43	402.6	106.05	402.6	89.42	402.6	89.42
2007	557.3	56.9	557.3	70.57	586.0	59.99	557.3	83.01	586.0	46.97	586.0	45.11
2008	823.7	129.01	823.7	157.41	823.7	183.12	823.7	182.24	823.7	148.86	823.7	144.50
2009	984.1	320.58	984.1	368.31	951.3	347.61	984.1	403.82	951.3	302.86	951.3	300.33
2010	886	211.26	886	246.36	682.6	129.72	886	275.93	682.6	101.58	682.6	100.13
2011	820.8	239.34	820.8	278.49	672.5	186.81	820.8	310.78	672.5	163.81	672.5	163.30
2012	474.8	101.2	474.8	126.46	421.2	165.25	474.8	141.63	421.2	143.98	421.2	143.75
Avg	843.6	184.8	843.6	219.2	758.5	234.6	843.6	245.09	758.5	179.2	758.5	173.9

Table 1.8. Sub-Watershed wise runoff (mm) estimated for Harohalli watershed

Year WS no.	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005
1	330.91	368.06	520.71	324.82	13.91	180.17	240.43	406.22
2	241.03	261.89	409.55	243.82	6.59	106.97	175.55	289.27
3	259.44	283.82	433.02	242.66	7.7	120.77	188.36	312.98
4	418.08	400.60	337.22	251.25	201.47	35.87	194.4	286.05
5	175.00	381.32	386.82	170.28	90.27	32.65	306.11	330.63
6	294.23	242.46	230.97	192.56	35.16	54.78	280.24	300.71
7	335.08	285.95	319.29	227.06	44.29	66.46	317.54	349.04
8	181.89	794.95	400.97	174.61	94.30	34.55	316.52	343.47
9	368.64	322.36	358.32	255.90	52.48	76.80	348.31	390.11
10	167.04	362.77	342.08	154.92	77.48	28.42	270.0	286.95
11	151.00	324.71	336.04	154.78	76.25	26.45	268.39	285.23
Total	2922.34	4028.89	4074.99	2392.66	699.9	763.89	2905.85	3580.66
Average	265.67	366.26	370.45	217.52	63.63	69.44	264.17	325.52
Minimum	151.00	242.46	230.97	154.78	6.59	26.45	175.55	285.23
Maximum	418.08	794.95	520.71	324.82	201.47	180.17	348.31	406.22

Year WS no.	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
1	68.41	132.24	275.43	275.14	111.32	212.07	99.87
2	42.05	87.25	199.72	200.41	73.85	153.96	70.31
3	46.89	95.78	215.16	215.52	75.49	165.69	76.28
4	30.59	198.94	265.66	323.86	156.68	195.81	114.36
5	102.76	56.65	125.72	340.54	123.02	181.69	160.62
6	82.11	56.90	129.01	320.58	211.26	239.34	101.20
7	95.31	70.57	157.41	368.31	246.36	278.49	126.46
8	106.43	59.99	183.12	347.61	129.72	186.81	165.25
9	106.05	83.01	182.24	403.82	275.93	310.78	141.63
10	89.42	46.97	148.86	302.86	101.58	163.81	143.98
11	89.42	45.11	144.50	300.33	100.13	163.30	143.75
Total	859.44	933.41	2026.83	3398.98	1605.34	2251.75	1343.71
Average	78.130	84.86	184.26	308.99	145.94	204.70	122.16
Minimum	30.59	45.11	125.72	200.41	73.85	153.96	70.31
Maximum	106.43	198.94	275.43	403.82	275.93	310.78	165.25

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The watershed is characterized by high rainfall, with irregular and erratic rainfall pattern. Surface runoff, the important parameter in the water balance equation, other than rainwater and infiltration (recharging factor to the soil as soil moisture) is necessary for efficient planning and management of the available water. The SCS curve number method uses, minimum data as input, and gives reliable output by using remote sensing and GIS techniques in most efficient way. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the performance of the procedure using land cover database from remotely

sensed data. From the Table 1.8 it is observed that during the year 1999 maximum runoff of 794.95mm has occurred in the watershed 8. It was also observed that the minimum runoff of 6.59mm has occurred in the year 2002 for watershed 2. The values of correlation coefficients are very high for all the watersheds and it varies from 0.560 to 0.833. Hence, it can be said that there is a strong positive linear dependence between the annual rainfall and annual runoff and it can be observed that in the regression equation as the values of slope increases the runoff generated also increases. In this context, the highest slope value of 0.502 was obtained in the watershed 8 and hence it has produced more runoff in all the years (Table 1.8). Similarly for the watershed 6 the slope value was 0.301 and the runoff generated from this watershed is minimum for all the years. The runoff estimation carried out by using SCS curve number method will help in proper planning and management of catchment yield for better planning of river basin.

Computation of runoff which is balance of rainwater and the infiltration responsible for recharging the soil moisture is required for effective management of rainfed area. The inclusion of watershed characteristics such as soils, land use / land cover topography etc. in GIS software improves the accuracy and most importantly. The GIS method estimating runoff will tend to be advantageous if study area large or numerous, runoff is modeled repetitively with alternate land use / land cover. Curve number estimation using remotely sensed data has been shown to be more cost effective than conventional procedures.

References

1. Amutha R. and Porchelvan. P. (2009) Estimation of Surface Runoff in Malattar Sub – Watershed using SCS – CN Method, *Journal Indian Soc. Remote Sensing*, Vol. 37, pp. 291 – 304.
2. Burrough, P. A. (1986) *Principles of Geographic Information Systems for Land Resources Assessment*, Clarendon Press, Oxford.
3. Chopra Rajiv, Raman Deep Dhiman and Sharma P. K. (2005) Morphometric Analysis of Sub – watershed in Gurdaspur District, Punjab using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques., *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 33, pp.531 – 539.
4. Chow V.T., Maidment, D.R., and Mays W., (1988). *Applied Hydrology*, Mc Graw Hill, New York.
5. C. T. Anuradha and S. Prabhavathy (2010), *Water Resources Management for Virudhunagar District using Remote Sensing and GIS*, p 5561, *International Journal of Earth Sciences and Engineering*, 3(1) Spl issue, January 2010.
6. Carlos Henrique Grohmann 'Morphometric analysis in geographic information systems: Applications of free software GRASS'2004,p1055-167.
7. Clarke J. I., (1966) *Morphometry from Maps, Essays in Geomorphology*, Elsevier Publ. Co., New York, pp. 235-274.
8. Druva Narayan, (1996) Design of earth dams for water harvesting and erosion control in Shiwaliks, *Journal of Institute of Engineers*.
9. Dutta Dushmata and Rabin Bhattarai, (2007) Estimation of Soil Erosion and Sediment Yield using GIS at Catchment Scale, *Water Resource Management*, Vol. 21, pp. 1635 – 1647.
10. Das D. C. and Mukherjee B. K. (1980) *National Perspective on Soil and Moisture Conservation*, *Agriculture Engineering Today*, Vol. 4,
11. ESRI (1994), *Map Projections–Georeferencing Spatial Data*, Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc. New York Street, Redlands, USA.
12. George Joseph, (2003) *Fundamentals of Remote Sensing*, Universities Press (India) Private Ltd.
13. Horton R.E., (1932) *Drainage Basin Characteristics*, *Transaction of the American Geophysical Union*, Vol. 13, pp. 350-361.
14. Horton R.E., (1945) *Erosional development of streams and their drainage basins: Hydrophysical approach to quantitative morphology*, *Bull. Geological Society of America*, Vol. 56, pp. 275-370.
15. Hawkins R. H. (1993) *Asymptotic determination of runoff curve numbers from data*, *Journal of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, ASCE*, Vol. 119(2), pp. 334 -345.
16. Hjelmfelt A. T. (1991) *Investigation of curve number procedure*, *Journal of Hydraulic Engineering, ASCE*, Vol. 117(6), pp. 725 – 737.
17. *Integrated Mission for Sustainable Development (IMSD), Technical Guidelines*, Department of space NRSA (1995), Hyderabad.
18. ISRO–NNRMS–TR–103–2002, *Regional Remote Sensing Center (2002), Watershed characterization, prioritisation development, planning and monitoring – Remote Sensing approach*, Indian Space Research Organisation, Bangalore.